

ISic1526

I.Sicily inscription 1526

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15537

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κυρακῆ
2. ἐνθάδε κεῖ
3. τε ἐζήσε ἔτη
4. βλ ἐτάφη ἕξσκ
5. τοῦ Ὀκτωβ(ρίου)

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1896

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645026

PHI 333249

Bibliography

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